

Significantly overestimated electron and hole mobilities of Te and Bi₂S₃ thin-film transistors in A. Liu et al., Nat. Commun. 13, 6372 (2022).

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V. Bruevich and V. Podzorov

Dept. of Physics & Astronomy, Rutgers, the State University of New Jersey, 136 Frelinghuysen Rd., Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA.

E-mails: bruevich@physics.rutgers.edu, podzorov@physics.rutgers.edu

A post-publication peer review on:

Ao Liu, Huihui Zhu, Taoyu Zou, Youjin Reo, Gi-Seong Ryu, Yong-Young Noh, Evaporated nanometer chalcogenide films for scalable high-performance complementary electronics, *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 6372 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-34119-6>

Main claims of the original paper:

n-type Bi₂S₃ thin-film transistors (TFTs) with electron mobilities of 12.5 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹, and *p*-type Te TFTs with hole mobilities of over 50 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹.

Device parameters:

(a) Gate: heavily-doped Si wafer;

(b) Gate dielectric: 40 nm-thick HfO₂ (which means that the correct capacitance per unit area should be $C_i = 553 \text{ nF/cm}^2$, as the static dielectric constant of ALD-grown HfO₂ is $\epsilon = 25$ (see, e.g., J. Robertson, High dielectric constant gate oxides for metal oxide Si transistors. *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **69**, 327 (2006), <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/69/2/R02>);

(c) Channel dimensions (as given in Methods for both Bi₂S₃ and Te TFTs): $L = 100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $W = 800 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Analysis details:

1. *p*-type Te TFTs.

TFT mobilities reported in this work appear to be severely exaggerated (by a factor of $\sim 10 - 30$, depending on the type of devices). For the optimized (best performing) tellurium (Te) TFT, the properly extracted *hole* mobility is in the range $1.5 - 3.4 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

First, it turns out an overestimated L/W ratio has been used in this paper for mobility calculations. The channel length and width stated are $L = 100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $W = 800 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (for both types of TFTs – see Methods), but the actual device photo (Fig. 1a, reproduced below) shows that $L = 90 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $W = 945 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The overestimated L/W ratio alone would lead to a mobility overestimation by a factor of ~ 1.32 (by 32%).

Fig. 1a

Scale bar is stated to be $100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$

The actual channel dimensions are:
 $L = 90 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $W = 945 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $L/W = 0.095$

The dimensions given in the paper:
 $L = 100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $W = 800 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $L/W = 0.125$

The overestimated L/W ratio alone would lead to a $> 30\%$ of mobility overestimation.

The L and W dimensions are stated to be the same for both Bi_2S_3 and Te TFTs.

Second, the mobilities properly extracted from the transfer curve of the optimized *p*-type Te TFT (Fig. 4d), even when using an overestimated L/W ratio $100/800 = 0.125$, are much smaller than the stated $50 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. See plots below showing our analysis of the digitized original data.

Fig. 4 | Electrical characterizations of RT evaporated Te TFTs and inverters.
d Transfer curves of optimized 100 °C-annealed Te TFT measured at linear and saturation regions.

The two Figures below show the plots of digitized transfer curve from the original Fig. 4d in two regimes (red and blue curves) fitted with the full Shockley FET/MOSFET model (solid line). The parameters used and the extracted hole mobility values are indicated on the plots.

The Figure below is an attempt to determine the “mobility” of this p -type TFT in the saturation regime (the red curve in the original Fig. 4d) by using the method of taking a derivative of the so-called “square-root curve”. Of course, such a method is improper if dealing with non-linear square-root curves (and, indeed, $|I_{DS}|^{1/2}(V_{GS})$ dependence for this TFT is highly non-linear). Nevertheless, below we still use this analysis method to see if that was the way the authors arrived to a mobility of $50 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The result is shown on the plot.

"Mobility" extracted via derivative of transfer curve (sat. regime)

Based on this analysis, hole mobility of the optimized Te TFT, properly extracted from the data presented in the paper, is in the range:

$$\mu = 1.5 - 3.4 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1},$$

which suggests that the mobility of these devices reported in this work ($50 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) is severely overestimated.

2. n-type Bi_2S_3 TFTs.

Digitizing original Fig. 1b for the optimized Bi_2S_3 TFT and calculating the field-effect mobility μ for this device using the Shockley MOSFET model results in a significantly lower μ than that claimed in the paper. The Figure below shows the red curve (annealing done at 250°C) isolated and digitized.

Fitting this transfer curve with the standard Shockley MOSFET model (see Figure below) yields an electron mobility of:

$$\mu = 1.56 \pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1},$$

which is almost an order of magnitude smaller than the mobility claimed for this TFT in the paper ($12.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$).

It is unclear why the authors used only the *saturation* regime for the mobility extraction in this case, and why only measurements at a single value of the source-drain voltage ($V_{DS} = 10 \text{ V}$) were carried out. The authors did not explain why only one curve and one set of parameters were used or how these were selected. Such an approach commonly leads to errors in mobility evaluation in transistors.

It has been recently shown that, in a number of papers on various types of TFTs published by this group, the authors used improper practices of mobility extraction, typically taking advantage of a sharp spike in the derivative of a noisy, nonlinear transfer curve for a selected device, and/or using a significantly underestimated gate-channel capacitance, C_i , or W/L ratio for their devices. See, e.g., the following analyses:

1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-024-01154-8>,
2. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11209050>,
3. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10315445>,
4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10445238>,
5. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10046993>.

To check if, in the case of these n -type Bi_2S_3 TFTs, a sharp spike in the derivative of the transfer curve has been used for the μ extraction again, we have created a plot below for the “mobility” (wrongly) calculated from the derivative of the MOSFET model vs. the gate voltage.

This plot shows that even when the mobility is calculated by using the improper method (taking advantage of the highest spike in the derivative, $\partial I_{\text{DS}}^{1/2}(V_{\text{GS}})/\partial V_{\text{GS}}$), μ as high as that reported by the authors cannot be obtained. It is simply impossible to reach $12.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ with the published data and the relevant device parameters. Since the authors used a non-typical gate dielectric in these TFTs, the erroneous (over-inflated) mobility is probably, in part, a result of using a grossly underestimated gate-channel capacitance. The authors have not provided any information on characterization of electrical properties of their gate dielectric layer.

Conclusion:

The charge carrier mobilities reported in this paper for n -type Bi_2S_3 TFTs ($12.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) and p -type Te TFTs ($50 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) appear to be *severely* overestimated. The actual mobilities consistent with the published data are approximately 1.56 and $3.4 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for the Bi_2S_3 and Te TFTs, respectively.

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